

Entrepreneurship skills for students with learning disabilities: A review from Malaysian National Curriculum

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received Jan 3, 2022 Revised Jan 20, 2022 Accepted: 15 March 2022 Published: 1 April 2022</p>	<p>Entrepreneurship skills are the most powerful weapon to drive entrepreneurial spirit and give practical competencies that enable students with learning disabilities to start their own businesses. Therefore, sustaining entrepreneurship skills are an effective venture to enhance an independent and productive living for students with learning disabilities. The purpose of this study is to contribute to the fundamental knowledge on entrepreneurship skills emphasized by the Ministry of Education Malaysia as an element across the curriculum for students with learning disabilities. However, entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities remain behind in terms of research and importance. Thus, more researches are very crucial in this field. Reviews of relevant literature in articles using search engines are the main methodology in this study. Total six most relevant articles were selected out of 178 articles after the screening process. As a result, there are five entrepreneurship skills listed by the Ministry of Education Malaysia to be achieved through elements across the curriculum in teaching and learning activities for students with learning disabilities. The impact of this study provides the literature review on entrepreneurship skills to future researchers.</p>
<p>Keywords: Entrepreneurship Entrepreneurship skills Students with learning disabilities</p>	

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INTRODUCTION (11 PT)

Entrepreneurship skills are considered as an opportunity or alternative pathway for students with learning disabilities to involve in the job market in developed countries. (Widoyoko et al., (2018). According to the Learning Disabilities Association of Canada (2017), students with learning disabilities referred to those who are having retardation, disorder, or delayed development in any one or more of the processes of speech, language, reading, spelling, writing, or arithmetic. These include students with ADHD, autism, down syndrome, mental retardation, dyslexia, and slow learner (Norfishah Mat Rabi, 2020). On the other hand, World Health Organization revealed there are currently more than 2 billion people confirmed as people with disabilities, which is 37.5% of the world's population (Lise Wagner, 2019). In Malaysia, based on Special Education Data ended 31 January 2020, it was found that a total of 88,352 students were categorized as students with special needs. Based on the data, the number of students with learning disabilities is very worrying. This is because a total of 72,683 students were categorized as students with learning disabilities out of 88,352 students with special needs, which is 82 % of the total number of students with learning disabilities. Currently, this situation in Malaysia reflects a global reality, where more people are suffering from disabilities and the number of people with disabilities may increase over time.

Moreover, the unemployment rate remains a major problem among students with learning disabilities (Rohaizat, Mohd Hanafi & Nabil, 2016). This is evident when the Malaysian Government has allocated 1% of employment opportunities in the public sector to People with Disabilities in the Service Circular No. 10/1988, yet only 1,754 were managed to fill jobs in the ministry compared to the 60,000 disabled people who could work (Public Service Department, 2013). Malaysian Educational Blue Print (2013-2025) shows a total of 1,934 students with special needs from educational schools unemployed in 2012. This data clearly shows that the majority of students with learning disabilities in Malaysia are still unemployed.

As prevention for unemployment issues, developing countries promote entrepreneurship education or skills through the education system to prepare students with learning disabilities to become an entrepreneur at the same time contribute to the nation's economy. Meanwhile, entrepreneurship skills are able to break down the problems faced by students with learning disabilities especially in getting a permanent job. Students with learning disabilities who acquire entrepreneurship skills are able to create their own jobs. Entrepreneurship skills will step up their abilities to be a "job creator" rather than a "job seeker". In addition, the applied entrepreneurship skills are able to build alternative ideas and creativity to create jobs and not rely on salaried jobs alone (Anizam et al., 2020). This in turn can overcome the unemployment issues among students with learning disabilities. Thus, entrepreneurship skills should be tailored among students with learning disabilities in the curriculum of primary schools. Therefore, special education teachers need to cultivate entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities through educational activities and training in line with the Malaysian National Curriculum.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurs and Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurs have certain identifiable attributes. According to the statement of peace activist Mahatma Gandhi, "Creative, active people keep society, culture and the economy moving and in constant development. Every person, regardless of age, profession, or social status, is challenged to work for

positive. People who take on this task can be described as entrepreneurs". The word derived from the French which means "undertaking" but according to the definition of Schumpeter (1911), it should not only be translated as "entrepreneur" but also as "key drivers of economic and social dynamics" (Lindner, 2018). Additionally, Schumpeter (1911) highlighted an entrepreneur as an individual who introduces new products and services, creates new forms of organization, or exploits new raw material. On the other hand, the entrepreneur is commonly seen as an innovator or a source of new ideas. This is supported by Lumpkin and Dess (2001), who mentioned that entrepreneurs have the innovative skills to enhance new values to their own business.

In consequence, an innovative entrepreneur plays an important role to upgrade the economics of an individual as well as contributing to the country. According to Gelaidan and Abdullateef (2017), entrepreneurs are able to produce new ideas, able to transform the ideas into a profitable business, create innovative processes, and produce employment. However, Rahim et al., (2015) found there are some common similarities on the definitions of entrepreneurs agreed by the scholars although there are differing definitions. Mainly, scholars stated that an entrepreneur is someone with the unique instinct to see change as an opportunity for value creation. Scholars identified that entrepreneurs are visionary, able to conceptualize and implement business plans, and possess an inspirational mindset.

Entrepreneurship is defined as a skill to start a new business. Besides, the entrepreneur is an individual who creates a new business, bearing most of the risks and enjoying most of the rewards. In other words, the process of setting up a business is known as entrepreneurship (Lindner, 2018). Meanwhile, Low and McMillan (1998) define entrepreneurship as the creation of new enterprises. Thus, enterprise and entrepreneurship are interrelated in the effort of developing employability for the graduates (O'Leary, 2015). Though Shane and Venkataraman (2007) mentioned entrepreneurship does not have to include the creation of new organizations, it can also occur in existing organizations. Bruyat and Julien (2000), explain entrepreneurship is a process that brought changes, that lead to the generation of new values, whereas an entrepreneur is a business founder. Besides, entrepreneurship is a dynamic process of vision, change, and creation. it demands the use of energy and passion to create and implement new ideas as well as creative proposals (Kuratko, 2005). Moreover, an entrepreneur is one who manages, administers, and bears the risks of a business.

In the context of students with learning disabilities, they are able to think like an entrepreneur and produce ideas innovatively in their own business to upgrade the economy at the same time producing employment. It encompasses networking skills, idea creation, developing and implementing a business plan, running a business, and evaluating the internal and external business environment. In terms of students with learning disabilities, entrepreneurship is a knowledge and skill to set up a business. On the whole, entrepreneurship is where the students with learning disabilities able to develop their skills and abilities in the independent development and implementation of ideas and point out their innovative power, which encompasses the creation of new products, production processes, organizational structures, or alternative ways.

Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship education is not something new to the education system. The idea of infusing entrepreneurship into education has spurred much in the last few decades. As a result, entrepreneurship education enhanced economic growth, job creation, individual growth, improved school involvement, and improved equality. Although, there is also an important question of whether entrepreneurship can be encouraged through education (Sanchez & Sahuquillo, 2018). According to Ivanov et al. (2012), education is the only platform that plays an essential role in the evolution of an entrepreneurial society. Entrepreneurial education is a source to provide concepts, skills, knowledge and build their self-esteem to grab job opportunities (Zahari et al., 2018). Nevertheless, many universities and educational

institutions provide entrepreneurship training programs to develop entrepreneurship skills among the students (Rosa Maria et al., 2019).

Students with Learning Disabilities

Students with learning disabilities are individuals diagnosed with difficulties in reading, writing, speaking, listening, spelling, reasoning, or doing math. Students with learning disabilities have problems in receiving information through their senses. Thus, they face difficulties in processing the information accurately. According to Law on Individual with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA), (2004) learning problems occur in one or more problems occur in basic psychological processes in writing or spoken language. The definition of learning disabilities is in line with the IDEA proposed by Sana Ali & Rafi (2016). Learning disability is retardation, disorder, or delayed development in any one or more of the processes of speech, language, reading, spelling, writing, or arithmetic. These problems are due to disorder or deficiency in any one or more of the basic psychological processes involved in understanding or in the use of spoken or written language.

According to the Learning Disabilities Association of Canada (2017), learning disabilities refer to a number of disorders that may affect the organization, acquisition, retention, understanding, or use of verbal or nonverbal information. These disorders affect learning in individuals with disabilities otherwise display at least average abilities essential for thinking and reasoning. Besides, learning disabilities may cause impairments in one or more processes related to perceiving, thinking, remembering, or learning. These include, but are not limited to language processing, phonological processing, visual-spatial processing, processing speed, memory and attention, and executive functions. Department of development of people with disabilities, department of social welfare (2011) defines learning disabilities as brain intelligence that is inconsistent with its biological age. Those who fall into this category are students with late global development, down syndrome, and intellectual disabilities. This category also includes conditions that affect an individual's learning ability such as autism, ADHD, specific learning difficulties such as dyslexia, dyscalculia, dysgraphia, and mental retardation.

In short, students with learning disabilities can be categorized either by the type of information processing or by the specific difficulties caused by a processing deficit. Learning disabilities can be categorized within four broad categories such as spoken language, written language, arithmetic, and reasoning. Students with learning disabilities can succeed in their life only with proper guidance, recognition, and intervention.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, a few methods have been used. Reviews of relevant literature are the main methodology in this study. The initial step was to analyses related papers and try to relate entrepreneurship skills and students with learning disabilities. Within this process, relevant articles were sought from search engines including Science Direct (<http://www.sciencedirect.com/>), Taylor & Francis (<http://www.tandfonline.com/>), Sage Publications (<http://www.sagepub.com/home.nav>), Emerald Publishing (<http://www.emeraldinsight.com/>) and some of the journals were also assessed and downloaded at trusted sites such as ResearchGate (<https://www.researchgate.net/>) and Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.com/>). Keywords such as 'entrepreneurship skills for students with learning disabilities', 'entrepreneurship education for students with learning disabilities', 'entrepreneurship competencies', and 'entrepreneurship skills in Malaysian National Curriculum' were used in the process of searching articles. These efforts resulted in the identification of 178 articles; however, only 46 remained after the second stage of the screening process. A total of 26% of the articles were related to entrepreneurship skills and students with learning disabilities while the remainder were linked to

entrepreneurship education in general. Most of the selected articles focused on entrepreneurship education and the skills in other Asian and European countries, Africa countries, and Australia, while a small number of articles related to entrepreneurship skills for students with learning disabilities in Malaysia. A total of six articles were identified as the main references on entrepreneurship skills and entrepreneurship education in Malaysia for students with learning disabilities, while the remaining articles provide supportive information on entrepreneurship education.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Implementation of Entrepreneurial Competencies in Malaysian National Curriculum

The purpose of entrepreneurship education is to evolve entrepreneurial competencies through educational activities indirectly. Entrepreneurial competencies were interpreted as knowledge, skills, and attitudes (Lackeus, 2015). There are three main themes in entrepreneurial competencies that affect the ability to be a successful entrepreneur. Therefore, entrepreneurship skills are under the umbrella of entrepreneurial competencies.

According to Farrington et al., (2012) entrepreneurial competencies can be categorized into cognitive competencies and non-cognitive competencies. Cognitive competencies are very easy to teach and evaluate, whereas non-cognitive competencies require learning by doing and are more difficult to evaluate (Moberg, 2014a). However, current educational policies emphasizing large-scale assessment and the international standardized test has led to giving importance to cognitive competencies than non-cognitive competencies. The researchers identified the negative impacts that occur due to neglected non-cognitive competencies among entrepreneurs or students (Farrington et al., 2012). Table 1 shows the entrepreneurial competencies and their sub-themes accordingly with the interpretation.

Table 1: Framework Outlining Some Key Entrepreneurial Competencies and Their Relation to Cognitive and Non-Cognitive Competencies.

	Main themes	Sub themes	Interpretation
Non-Cognitive competencies Cognitive competencies	Knowledge	Mental models	Knowledge on how to resolve without resources
		Declarative Knowledge	Knowledge on basic entrepreneurship, value creation, idea generation, marketing risk
		Self-insight	Knowledge on personal on how to be an entrepreneur
	Skills	Marketing skills	Marketing products, persuasion, dealing with customers, communicating for a vision
		Resource skills	Create business plan, financial plan, obtaining financing
		Opportunity skills	Recognizing and looking for business opportunity, Product/service/concept development skills
		Interpersonal skills	Leadership, give motivation to others, managing people, socializing
		Learning skills	Be an active learner, adopt new situations
		Strategic skills	Set a goal and focus on goals, defining a vision,
		Entrepreneurial passion	“I want”, Need for achievement

Attitudes	Self-efficacy	“I can”, Belief in one’s ability to perform given tasks
	Entrepreneurial identity	“I am/I value”, Deep belief, Role identity, Values
	Proactiveness	“I do” Action oriented, proactive
	Uncertainty/ambiguity tolerance	“I dare”. comfortable with uncertainty, adaptable
	Innovativeness	“I create”. Innovativeness, creative
	Perseverance	“I overcome”. Ability to overcome

Source: Adapted from (Lackeus, 2014)

Based on table 1, there are six sub-themes highlighted as entrepreneurship skills, which are marketing skills, resource skills, opportunity skills, interpersonal skills, learning skills, and strategic skills.

Entrepreneurship skills in the Malaysian National Primary School Standard Curriculum as an Element Across the Curriculum through all the subjects for students with learning disabilities

Ministry of Education emphasizes entrepreneurship skills in the Primary School Standard Curriculum through teaching and learning activities so that it becomes a culture in their daily lives (Curriculum Development Division MOE, 2011). There are five main objectives of the entrepreneurship skills highlighted by the Curriculum Development Division as follows:

1. Practice an entrepreneurial attitude
2. Practice a way of thinking towards entrepreneurship in necessary situations
3. Practice simple basic sales management knowledge and skills in relevant activities of daily living
4. Produce knowledge-based products as well as technological and vocational skills
5. Practice good moral and ethical values in the context of entrepreneurship

Besides that, table 2 summarizes the main objectives and focus of entrepreneurship skills in the Primary School Standard Curriculum through teaching and learning activities.

Table 2: The Main Objectives and Focus of Entrepreneurial Elements Highlighted by Ministry of Education Malaysia.

Main Objectives	Focus
1. Practice an entrepreneurial attitude	Responsible for decisions
	Aware to the opportunities
	Dare to take estimated risks
	Creativity and innovation
	Flexibility
	Desire for immediate feedback
	Future oriented

	Willingness to learn from mistakes
	Capable of leading
	Achievement oriented
	Resilient
	Tolerant of high uncertainty
	High perseverance
	Can build social networks
2. Practice a way of thinking towards entrepreneurship in necessary situations	<p>Students need to be critical, creative and innovative.</p> <p>This will help them identify opportunities in the environment, so that they can continue to succeed or at least survive by their efforts.</p>
3. Practice simple basic sales management knowledge and skills in relevant activities of daily living	<p>Students can master the basic knowledge and skills of simple sales management if they constantly exposed to the matter in teaching and learning activities.</p> <p>Students who have an attitude and way of thinking towards entrepreneurship, students can practice basic business management knowledge and skills in a simple transaction in relevant daily life situations.</p>
4. Produce knowledge -based products as well as technological and vocational skills	<p>Students who have learned a technique in their learning can create and produce competitive products based on technological and vocational knowledge according to their creativity.</p>
5. Practice good moral and ethical values in the context of entrepreneurship	<p>Practice good moral and ethical values in the context of entrepreneurship.</p> <p>The practice of good moral and ethical values in the context of entrepreneurship encourages students to behave responsibly to society.</p>

Source: Handbook of Entrepreneurship Education, Ministry of Education Malaysia (2011)

At the same time, the Curriculum Development Division of Malaysia implemented entrepreneurship education for students with learning disabilities as an element across the curriculum. There are some key points highlighted in the curriculum to achieve the aims of entrepreneurship education among students with learning disabilities in order to produce young entrepreneurs. There are similarities between the aims of entrepreneurship education for primary school and the aims of entrepreneurship education for students with learning disabilities.

“The application of entrepreneurial elements aims to shape the characteristics and practices of entrepreneurship to become a culture among students. Entrepreneurial characteristics can be applied through teaching and learning activities that can cultivate attitudes such as diligence, honesty, trust and responsibility as well as develop creative and innovative minds to drive ideas to market”.

Source: Curriculum Development Division, Ministry of Education Malaysia (2011)

In short, we can conclude that Curriculum Development Division, Ministry of Education Malaysia (2011) planned and designed the curriculum for students with learning disabilities to cultivate their entrepreneurship skills through the education system. The curriculum revealed the aim of entrepreneurship skills for the students with learning disabilities to develop their creative ideas in the job market.

DISCUSSIONS

Entrepreneurship education has become an important agenda in planning educational policies in many countries in this 21st century. Policy-makers had developed initiatives to enable and encourage students with learning disabilities to involve in entrepreneurial activities (Wittenburg et al., 2013). Numerous studies show entrepreneurship education is significant in cultivating the spirit of entrepreneurship among students with learning disabilities (Rahim et al., 2015). The most common reason for promoting entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities is because entrepreneurship is seen as an engine for economic growth and job creation. Thus, students with learning disabilities should acquire the entrepreneurship skills to be successful in their daily life. Therefore, the Ministry of Education Malaysia emphasizes five main objectives of teaching entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities.

The first objective of teaching entrepreneurship skills is to practice an entrepreneurial attitude among students with learning disabilities. The Ministry of Education Malaysia identified 14 attitudes to practice entrepreneurship skills as follows responsible for decisions, aware of the opportunities, dare to take estimated risks, creativity, and innovation, flexibility, desire for immediate feedback, future-oriented, willing to learn from mistakes, capable of leading, achievement-oriented, resilient, tolerant of high uncertainty, high perseverance and can build social networks. The students with learning disabilities should be responsible for the results they might face from entrepreneurial activities is closely related to the strength of the student's internal self-control. They should be aware to their own abilities and take the opportunities available in the surroundings to extend their business and enterprise. Students with learning disabilities need to learn to manage risk and ensure that the risks taken are reasonable and commensurate with the rewards received. Students with learning disabilities should practice creativity and innovative skills so that they are able to solve problems logically as well as be able to generate ideas that can be implemented in the form of innovation. Students with learning disabilities should practice an attitude of flexibility. This attitude will ensure the ability to adapt to changes in the environment into creativity and innovation. They must have a strong desire to use knowledge to improve their performance. This attitude is closely related to the desire to learn from past mistakes. Moreover, students with learning disabilities should be trained to be future-oriented. They must give exposure to future business patterns so that they will have a desire to get into entrepreneurship activities.

Besides that, failure is a lesson so that the same mistakes are not repeated. Thus, students with learning disabilities should practice themselves to accept failure as an impetus to achieve success. They should experience to lead, has knowledge of the technology and the environment. It is because leadership is very important to be a successful entrepreneur. Students with learning disabilities must know the objectives and goals to be achieved in a matter. Therefore, the objectives are an impetus to move students with learning disabilities towards achievement in entrepreneurship. They should practice daring to face various challenges and obstacles to succeed in a project or entrepreneurship activities. Students with learning disabilities need to have high mental, physical and emotional strength while continuing to deal with all problems encountered in the process of entrepreneurship with perseverance. They must continue to perform assigned tasks despite facing various possible situations as a result of not getting accurate information or unexpected changes. They need to have the patience to tolerate uncertain situations. Students with learning disabilities need to face various challenges to ensure success in their efforts. On the other hand, they can use social networks to forge collaborative relationships to obtain information or share resources to expand their entrepreneurship.

The second objective of teaching entrepreneurship skills is to practice a way of thinking towards entrepreneurship in necessary situations. The students with learning disabilities should practice themselves to think towards entrepreneurship around their surroundings and grab the opportunities. Therefore, they should have critical, creative, and innovative thinking to practice entrepreneurship. This will help them identify opportunities in the environment so that they can continue to succeed or at least survive by their efforts. Based on the Handbook of Entrepreneurship Education, the Ministry of Education Malaysia (2011) highlights the way of thinking towards entrepreneurship involves nine main steps, namely:

1. The practice of observing the environment intentionally and purposefully
2. Analyze observations critically and creatively
3. Generate ideas from observations
4. Choose the best idea from many ideas
5. Improve selected ideas in the form of innovations
6. Evaluate ideas critically in the context
7. Implement ideas in the form of abstract or concrete technological products
8. Adapting new ideas to the needs of society and the environment
9. Continuing to improve the quality of ideas

Students with learning disabilities should apply these nine steps to practice themselves to be an entrepreneur. These skills enable them to create opportunities to be a “job creator” rather than be a “job seeker”. Because, entrepreneurship skill is not just a skill acquisition whereas it is a skill to create employment for themselves and also for others (Omede et al., 2016). In another way, students with learning disabilities are able to think towards entrepreneurship around their surroundings and grab the opportunities to become self-employment. The self-employment activities conducted by them are collectively known as “necessity entrepreneurship” according to entrepreneurship literature (Williams & Round, 2009). Most people with learning disabilities choose for self-employment and start their own business with the skills they have (Maria et al., 2019). Studies strongly supported the benefits of self-employment among people with learning disabilities in different contexts. Europe and US data indicated self-employment rates higher than among people with disabilities. The Australian Bureau of Statistics (2013) shows that people with learning disabilities are more likely to run their own business than the normal person with a ratio of 11.6 to 8.2 %. In addition, Hwang & Roulstone (2015) found 388,241 out of 915,217 students with learning disabilities in South Korea identified as self-employed. Thus, entrepreneurship skills drive the students with learning disabilities to be self-employed and contribute to independent living.

Furthermore, Noraini et al., (2015) stated that the lack of skills in line with the wishes of employers is also a barrier factor for students with learning disabilities to get a job. Research shows students with learning disabilities do not have employability skills (Samian et al., 2013). In addition, existing employability skills through vocational education do not necessarily meet the needs of employers (Yusuf et al., 2013). Hence, entrepreneurship skills are crucial for students with learning disabilities to overcome unemployment issues. Consequently, the Ministry of Education Malaysia introduced the third objective of teaching entrepreneurship skills to practice simple basic sales management knowledge and skills in relevant activities of daily living. So that, students with learning disabilities can master the basic knowledge and skills of simple sales management if they are constantly exposed to the matter in teaching and learning activities. Students with learning disabilities who have an attitude and way of thinking towards entrepreneurship are able to practice basic business management knowledge and skills in a simple transaction in relevant daily life situations. The application of basic knowledge and management skill elements of buying and selling easily. The basic knowledge and management skills involve managing money either in daily expenses or savings, managing easy daily buying and selling transactions, and good consumerism practices. It seems the students with learning disabilities practice themselves to acquire sales management knowledge and skill through the learning activities in the classroom. Significantly, a study conducted by Anizam et al., (2020) has identified special education teachers integrate four elements which are sub-elements in entrepreneurial skills, namely product production skills, product marketing skills, business skills, and cost calculation skills through teaching and learning activities for the student with learning disabilities.

The fourth objectives of teaching entrepreneurship skills are to produce knowledge-based products as well as technological and vocational skills. These skills enable the students with learning disabilities to learn a technique in their learning to create and produce competitive products based on technological and vocational knowledge according to their creativity. Technological and vocational knowledge is crucial for students with learning disabilities to survive in the 21st century. They can apply the technological and vocational knowledge and skills to produce knowledge-based as well as technological and vocational products. Moreover, they will be able to produce the same product using different technologies. Otherwise, the technological and vocational knowledge and skills enable them to produce products using a variety of sources such as recycled sources. These entrepreneurship skills are able to cultivate the productivity of students with learning disabilities in terms of technological and vocational activities and change the employer's negative perception of students with learning disabilities. Research proved that employers labeled students with learning disabilities as unproductive people regardless of their education. According to Beisland et al. (2016), employers resist hiring people with learning disabilities because they underestimated their working capability. Employers expect those who are well trained and skilled in the entrepreneurial field to face industrial challenges. Thus, skill-based training and coaching are needed for students with learning disabilities to fulfill the employer's needs. Therefore, knowledge-based products, as well as technological and vocational skills, are compulsory because it is a form of skill-oriented education where the students are able to learn entrepreneurship skills through training and vocational activities. The fifth objectives of teaching entrepreneurship skills are to practice good moral and ethical values in the context of entrepreneurship among students with learning disabilities. Students with learning disabilities should practice good moral and ethical values in the context of entrepreneurship encourages them to behave responsibly to society. They should practice good moral and ethical values while handling the customers. There are five principles of good moral and ethical value practice in the context of entrepreneurship highlighted by the Ministry of Education Malaysia (2011) as shown in Framework 1.

Framework 1: The five principles of good moral and ethical value practice in the context of entrepreneurship highlighted by the Ministry of Education Malaysia (2011).

Students with learning disabilities should practice the principle of social responsibility. They must make sure the business or enterprise does not cause harm to humans and the environment. They should practice the principle of fairness. They should practice fair business to society. Besides, students with learning disabilities should understand human rights principles. They should practice respecting human rights. They should understand the principle of autonomy. Businesses cannot deny the right to choose individuals. At last, students with learning disabilities should practice the principle of transparency. They must ensure the business is not misleading.

However, competition and employment opportunities for students with learning disabilities are matters of debate in an effort to provide careers for this group of people. As a consequence, the government of Malaysia has taken the initiative to implement a career transition program for students with learning disabilities in secondary schools through a guideline for the special needs students' career transition program (Ministry of Education Malaysia Professional Circular No. 4, 2019). This career transition program is a form of effort to prepare students with learning disabilities to get employment opportunities as well as master vocational skills to qualify them for work. Nevertheless, researchers argue that vocational skills, employability, entrepreneurship skills should be applied through a systematic module from the grassroots again, starting at the primary school level.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In brief, sustaining entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities is a productive venture in this 21st century. As a developing country, Malaysia needs to cultivate entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities to be independent living by starting their own business with necessary competencies. Thus, this will enhance the country to produce more “job providers” rather than “job seekers”. Hence, society's perception of their physical ability and unemployment issues faced by students with learning disabilities will be prevented. Meanwhile, studies indicated that students who are immersed in entrepreneurial activities show a higher level of innovativeness in their work and are able to produce ideas in a new way. Therefore, entrepreneurship skills are crucial for students with learning disabilities to develop their skills in job creation, economic success, globalization, innovation, joy, engagement, creativity, and societal challenges (Lackeus, 2015). Educational activities and programs for students with learning disabilities should be tailored towards providing them with the needed entrepreneurship skills since primary school. This will ensure that students with learning disabilities grab employment opportunities and contribute to the nation’s economy.

Nevertheless, the aim of this study is to contribute to the fundamental knowledge on entrepreneurship skills emphasized by the Ministry of Education Malaysia through the Malaysian National Curriculum in the form of elements across the curriculum for students with learning disabilities. As a result, there are five main objectives of entrepreneurship skills listed by the Ministry of Education Malaysia to be achieved through elements across the curriculum in teaching and learning activities among students with learning disabilities. Therefore, educational institutions such as schools and universities play an effective role on produce students with greater entrepreneurship skills to acquire entrepreneurial attitudes (Mutluturk & Mardikyan, 2018; Dohse & Walter, 2012; Kusmintarti et al.,2018; Vanevenhoven & Liquori, 2013; Matlay, 2016; Henley et al., 2017). Future researchers may conduct research to explore more on the effectiveness of entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities.

REFERENCES

- [1] Anizam, M. Y., Manisah, M. A., Norhayati, M. N. (2020). Instilment of Employability Skills for Special Needs Students, *Online Journal for TVET Practitioners*, 5(1), 36-42. doi:10.30880/ojtp.2020.05.01.006
- [2] Australian Bureau Statistics, (2013). Statistics on people with learning disabilities and their own business. [Online]. Retrieved from: <https://www.abs.gov.au/>
- [3] Beisland, L. A., Mersland, R., & Zamore, S. (2016).“Motivations for Business Start-up: Are There Any Differences Between Disabled and Non-Disabled Microfinance Clients ?”. *Journal of International Development*, 28, 147-149. doi:10.1002/JID.3196
- [4] Bruyat, C., & Julien, P.A. (2000).“Defining the Field of Research in Entrepreneurship”. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 16(2), 165-80. Retrieved from: <http://www.sciepub.com/reference/122976>
- [5] Department of social welfare Malaysia, (2011). Department of development of people with disabilities.
- [6] Dohse, D., & Walter, S. G. (2012). Knowledge Context and Entrepreneurial Intentions Among Students. *Journal of Small Business Economics*, 39(4), 875-895. doi: 10.1007/s11187-011-9324-9
- [7] Farrington, C.A., Roderick, M., Allensworth, E., Nagaoka, J., Keyes, T.S., Johnson, D.W. & Beechum, N.O, (2012). Teaching Adolescents to Become Learners: The Role of Noncognitive

Factors in Shaping School Performance-A Critical Literature Review, The University of Chicago, ERIC.

- [8] Gelaidan, H., & Abdullateef, A. (2017). Entrepreneurial Intentions of Business Students in Malaysia the Role of Self-Confidence, Educational and Relation Support. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 24(1), 54-67. Retrieved from: <https://www.deepdyve.com/lp/emerald-publishing/entrepreneurial-intentions-of-business-students-in-malaysia-J0aVSUIo2a>
- [9] Rahim, H. L., Kadir, M. A., Abidin, Z. Z., Junid, J., Kamaruddin, L. M., Lajin, N. F., Buyong, S. Z., & Bakri, A. A. (2015). Entrepreneurship Education in Malaysia: A Critical Review. *Journal of Technology Management and Business*, 2(2), 1-11. Retrieved from: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/ENTREPRENEURSHIP-EDUCATION-IN-MALAYSIA%3A-A-CRITICAL-Rahim-Kadir/00208c1bc6c76d87707501dcc0243835d138e8dc>
- [10] Henley, Andrew, Contreras, Francoise, Espinosa, Juan C and Barbosa & David. (2017). Entrepreneurial Intentions of Colombian Business Students Planned Behaviour, Leadership Skills and Social Capital. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, vol. 23(6), 1017-1032. doi:10.1108/IJEBR-01-2017-0031
- [11] Hwang, S. K., & Roulstone, A. (2015). Enterprising? Disabled? The Status and Potential for Disabled People's Microenterprise in South Korea. *Journal of Disability & Society*, 30(1), 114-129. doi:10.1080/09687599.2014.993750
- [12] Ivanov, S., Svitlana, G., & Stepan, D. (2012). An Input of European Educational Standards at Higher School of Ukraine Modernisation of Educational System. *Journal of International Studies*, 5(2), 66-71. Retrieved from: <http://yadda.icm.edu.pl/yadda/element/bwmeta1.element.ekon-element-000171303435>
- [13] Kuratko, D. F. (2005). The Emergence of Entrepreneurship Education: Development, Trends, and Challenges. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 29, 577-598. doi:10.1111/j.1540-6520.2005.00099.x
- [14] Kusmintarti, A., Anshori, M. A., Sulasari, A., & Sidik, I. (2018). Students' Entrepreneur Profile: A Cluster of Student's Entrepreneurial Characteristics. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 21, 169-181. Retrieved from: <https://www.abacademies.org/articles/Students-entrepreneur-profile-a-cluster-of-students-entrepreneurial-characteristics-1528-2651-21-S1-169.pdf>
- [15] Lackéus, M. (2015). Entrepreneurship in Education: What, why, When, How, (*OECD Report*). [Online]. Retrieved from: https://www.oecd.org/cfe/leed/BGP_Entrepreneurship-in-Education.pdf
- [16] Lackeus, M. (2014). An Emotion-Based Approach to Assessing Entrepreneurial Education, *International Journal of Management Education*, 12(3), 374-396. doi:10.1016/j.ijme.2014.06.005
- [17] Learning Disabilities Association of Canada. (2017). Definition of Learning Disabilities. [Online]. Retrieved from: <https://www.ldac-acta.ca/>
- [18] Lise Wagner. (2019). Disabled People in the World: Facts and Figures. World Health Organization. [Online]. Retrieved from: <https://www.inclusivecitymaker.com/disabled-people-in-the-world-in-2019-facts-and-figures/>
- [19] Low, M., & McMillan, I. (1998). "Entrepreneurship: Past Research and Future Challenges". *Journal of Management*, 14 (2), 139-161. doi:10.1177%2F014920638801400202
- [20] Lumpkin, G. Tom., & Gregory G. Dess. (2001). Linking Two Dimensions of Entrepreneurial Orientation to Firm Performance: The Moderating Role of Environment and Industry Life Cycle. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 16(5), 429-451. doi:10.1016/S0883-9026(00)00048-3

- [21] Matlay, H. (2016). Critical Perspectives on Enterprise and Entrepreneurship Education Introduction. *Journal of Education and Training*, 58(7), 165-180. doi:10.1108/ET-06-2016-0108
- [22] Ministry of Education Malaysia (2013), Malaysian Education Blueprint (MEB), (2013-2025).
- [23] Ministry of Education Malaysia Professional Circular No. 4, (2019).
- [24] Ministry of Education Malaysia, (2011). Curriculum Development Division. Special Education Unit.
- [25] Ministry of Education Malaysia, (2011). Handbook of Entrepreneurship Education, Curriculum Development Division.
- [26] Ministry of Education Malaysia, (2020). Special Education Division, Special Education Data dated 31 January 2020. [Online]. Retrieved from :https://www.moe.gov.my/en/kuat-turun/pendidikankhas/buku-data-pendidikankhas/3993_buku-data-pendidikan-khas-tahun-2020/file
- [27] Moberg, K., (2014a). Assessing the Impact of Entrepreneurship Education- From ABC to PhD. *Doctoral Thesis Online*, Copenhagen Business School.
- [28] Mutluturk, Meltem, & Sona Mardikyan. (2018). Analysing Factors Affecting The Individual Entrepreneurial Orientation Of University Students. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*. 21, 165-180. Retrieved from: <https://www.abacademies.org/articles/Analysing-factors-affecting-the-individual-entrepreneurial-orientation-of-university-students-%201528-2651-21-S1-165.pdf>
- [29] Noor Aini Ahmad, (2015). Learning Identifying Alphabet Skill Through Activity Using Dough Shaping, *Malay Language Education Journal*, 5(1), 71-80. Retrieved from: http://journalarticle.ukm.my/8598/1/71-80_Noor_Aini_et_al.UPSI_0.pdf
- [30] Noraini, A., Mohd Hanafi, M.Y., & Nur Aishah, A. (2015). Implementation of the Inter- Agency Collaboration in Vocational Education of Students with Learning Disabilities Towards Preparation of Career Experience. *Journal of Asian Social Science*, 11(18), 183-192. doi: 10.5539/ass.v11n18p183
- [31] O'Leary, S. (2015). The Role of Enterprise and Entrepreneurship within Higher Education and Effective Economic Governance Across Central and Eastern Europe. *Journal of Economics and Sociology*. 8(2), 143-153. doi: 10.14254/2071- 789X.2015/8-2/11
- [32] Omede, A.A, (2010). Towards Providing Vocational and Technical Education for Person with Disability in Nigeria School and Colleges. *Journal of Advocacy and Rehabilitation in Special Education*, 8, 95-100.
- [33] Omede, Andrew.A, and Oguche Grace (2016). Entrepreneurship education for person with disabilities in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 8(16), 126-130. Retrieved from: www.iiste.org
- [34] Rosa Maria, M., Yolanda, S., Isidro, P., & Jesus David, S. P. (2019). Entrepreneurship Education and Disability: An Experience at A Spanish University. *Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 9(2), 34-45. doi:10.3390/admsci9020034
- [35] S Eko Putro Widoyoko, Budi Setiawan, Khabib Sholeh & Muh. Ibnu Shina. (2018). Model of entrepreneurship for people with disabilities. *1st International Conference on Law, Journal of Governance and Social Justice*, 54, 1-5. doi:10.1051/shsconf/20185406008
- [36] Samian, S.S., Ali, K. M., & Yahya, B. (2013). Employers' Perceptions of Employees with Disabilities in Organizations in the State of Johor. [Online]. Retrieved from

:http://eprints.utm.my/14948/1/Falsafah_Pendidikan_Kebangsaan_Memperkasakan_Peranan_Pendidikan_Teknik-eprint8.pdf.

- [37] Sana Ali & Mohammed Rafi. (2016). Learning disabilities: Characteristics and instructional approaches. *International Journal of Humanities Social Sciences and Education*, 3(4), 111-115. doi:10.20431/2349-0381.0304013
- [38] Schumpeter, J.A. (1911). The theory of economics development, *Harvard University Press*, Cambridge, MA: (English translation published in 1934).
- [39] Shane, S., & Venkataraman, S. (2007). The promise of entrepreneurship as field of research. *The Academy of Management Review Journal*, 25(1), 217-226. doi:10.2307/259271
- [40] Vanevenhoven, Jeff, & Eric Liquori. (2013). The Impact of Entrepreneurship Education: Introducing the Entrepreneurship Education Project. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 51(3), 315-328. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jsbm.12026>
- [41] Williams, Colin C., and John Round, (2009). Evaluating Informal Entrepreneurs' Motives: Evidence from Moscow. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*. 15(1), 94-107. doi: 10.1108/13552550910934477
- [42] Wittenburg, D., Mann, D, and Thompkins, A., (2013). The Disability System and Programs to Promote Employment for People with Disabilities. *IZA Journal of Labour Policy*, 2(4), 1-25. doi: 10.1186/2193-9004-2-4
- [43] Yusuf, K.K, (2013). Career Opportunity in Vocational and Technical Education for People with Special Needs. *Journal of New Perspectives in Special Needs Education for Sustainable Development*, 10(2), 132-138. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ598590.pdf>
- [44] Zahari, A. R., Puteri Fadzline, M. T., Azlinna, N. A., & Fariza Hashim. (2018). Student Spin-Off Intentions in Malaysia Higher Educational Institutions: Founders' Characteristics and University Roles. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 21(3), 1-15. Retrieved from: <https://www.thefreelibrary.com/The+Enablers+of+Student+SpinOffs+Intention%3A+A+Study+in+Malaysian...-a0567634667>